

9th International Conference on Control, Modelling, Computing and Applications (CMCA 2020)

August 22~23, 2020, Chennai, India

<https://www.csej.org/cmca/index.html>

Scope

9th International Conference on Control, Modelling, Computing and Applications (CMCA 2020) will provide an excellent international forum for sharing knowledge and results in theory, methodology and applications of Control Engineering, Modelling, Computing and Applications. The goal of this Conference is to bring together researchers and practitioners from academia and industry to focus on understanding Modern Control Engineering, Modelling and Computing concepts and establishing new collaborations in these areas.

Authors are solicited to contribute to the conference by submitting articles that illustrate research results, projects, surveying works and industrial experiences that describe significant advances in the areas of control engineering, modelling, computing & applications

Topics of Interest

- Adaptive Control
- Applications of Modelling in Science and Engineering
- Automation Systems
- Computer Controlled Systems
- Computer Vision
- Computational Science
- Control Devices and Instruments
- Control Theory
- Data Mining
- Design System and Algorithms
- Embedded Systems
- Fault Detection and Isolation
- Flight Control and Surveillance Systems
- Genetic Algorithms an Evolutionary Computing
- Guidance Control Systems
- Industry, Military and Space Applications
- Information Systems
- Linear and Nonlinear Control Systems
- Intelligent Control Systems
- Mathematical Modelling and Control
- Measurement Systems
- Multimedia Systems
- Networks and Communication
- Neural Networks and Fuzzy Logic
- Optimization and Optimal Control
- Process Control and Instrumentation
- Robotics
- Robust Control
- Scientific Computing

- Signal and Image Processing
- Simulation Techniques
- Soft Computing Techniques
- Stochastic Control and Filtering
- Systems and Automation
- System Identification and Control

Paper Submission

Authors are invited to submit papers through conference [Submission System](#) by **July 18, 2020**. Submissions must be original and should not have been published previously or be under consideration for publication while being evaluated for this conference. The proceedings of the conference will be published by [Computer Science Conference Proceedings](#) in [Computer Science & Information Technology \(CS & IT\)](#) series (Confirmed).

Selected papers from **CMCA 2020**, after further revisions, will be published in the special issue of the following journals

- [International Journal of Information Technology Convergence and Services \(IJITCS\)](#)
- [International Journal of Control Theory and Computer Modelling \(IJCTCM\)](#)
- [International Journal of Information Technology, Control and Automation \(IJITCA\)](#)
- [International Journal of Chaos, Control, Modelling and Simulation \(IJCCMS\)](#)
- [International Journal of Information Technology, modelling and Computing \(IJITMC\)](#)
- [Information Technology in Industry \(ITII\)](#) ^{New}-ESCI(WOS) Indexed

Important Dates

- **Submission Deadline : July 18, 2020**
- Authors Notification : August 10, 2020
- Registration & Camera-Ready Paper Due : August 13, 2020

Contact Us

Here's where you can reach us: cmca.confe@yahoo.com or cmca@cseij.org